

Synthesis and biological activity of some benzothiazolyl thiazolidinones

M. B. Deshmukh*, S. S. Jagtap, S. A. Deshmukh, S. D. Jadhav, P. V. Anbhule and A. W. Suryawanshi

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : m_deshmukhl@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 1 June 2006, accepted 22 March 2007

Abstract : A facile route for the synthesis of some thiazolidinone derivatives incorporating a benzothiazole moiety has been reported. *S*-(2-Propanoyl)-1,3-benzothiazole (2) was synthesized by reacting 2-mercapto benzothiazole with chloroacetone in dry acetone, which was subsequently reacted with substituted aryl hydrazides to give the corresponding hydrazones (3). These on cyclocondensation with mercaptoacetic acid in presence of glacial acetic acid yielded targeted series of benzothiazolyl thiazolidinones (4).

Keywords : Heterocycles, thiazolidinone.

Benzothiazoles and thiazolidinone show wide spectrum of biological activities and the former have varieties of industrial applications¹. In the present study we have introduced five membered thiazolidinone ring in the benzothiazole moiety with intention to obtain new compounds with improved biological activities.

The strategy employed for the synthesis of desired compounds involved the reaction of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole with chloroacetone to afford *S*-(2-propanoyl)-1,3-benzothiazole (2). The IR spectra shows band in the region of 1710 cm⁻¹ due to >C=O and ¹H NMR spectra shows singlet at δ 2.15 and singlet at δ 4.1 due to CH₃ and S-CH₂ respectively. Compound 2 on reaction with various aryl hydrazides afford compound 3a-i. The appearance of absorption band at 1620 and 1680 cm⁻¹ due to C=N and CONH respectively, confirmed the structure. The ¹H NMR spectra showed two singlets encountered at δ 2.4 and 3.8 due to CH₃ and S-CH₂ respectively. A broad singlet in the range of δ 9-10 confirmed presence of -NH. Further treatment of 3 with mercaptoacetic acid in presence of glacial acetic acid gave corresponding thiazolidinone derivatives 4a-i. The IR spectra shows absorption band at 1734 cm⁻¹ due to five membered ketone, 1680 cm⁻¹ due to amide CO and 3300 cm⁻¹ due to NH. The ¹H NMR spectrum shows two singlets at δ 3.7 and 4.6 due to cyclic S-CH₂ and S-CH₂ respectively. A broad singlet observed in the range between δ 11 to 13 confirmed the structure.

Biological activity of compounds :

Synthesized compounds were screened for their anti-

bacterial activity against gram positive (*Bacillus subtilis* and *S. aureus*) and gram negative (*Salmonella paratyphi* and *Pseudomonas spp*) bacteria. The test microorganisms were grown for 24 h at 37 °C in a buffered nutrient agar. A 24 h old culture of test micro-organism was added to the medium, a sterile paper disc (6 mm) prepared in a solution of test compound with concentration 100 mg/ml of DMF was placed over it and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. A control experiment was also run in a similar manner using the solvent. The antibacterial activity exhibited by the test compounds is depicted in terms of diameter of zone of inhibition : inactive (less than 13 mm), less active (13-16 mm), moderately active (17-20 mm) and highly active (21-27 mm) respectively. The analytical data of antibacterial activity of selected compounds have been given in Table 1. Most of the tested compounds exhibited spectacular activities against test bacterial species.

Experimental

All m.p.s were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on Shimadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer (cm⁻¹) and ¹H NMR spectra were scanned on a Bruker A-300 F-NMR spectrometer (chemical shifts in δ ppm) using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel G. All the compounds showed satisfactory microanalytical results for C, H, and N.

S-(2-Propanoyl)-1,3-benzothiazole (2) :

The mixture of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole 1 (0.1 mmol)

Table 1. Physical and antibacterial activity data for compounds (4a-i)

Compd.	R	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. formula	<i>Salmonella</i> <i>paratyphi</i>	<i>Bacillus</i> <i>subtilis</i>	<i>Pseudomonas</i> <i>spp</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
4a	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	205	72	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₃ O ₂ Cl	17.00	19.00	15.00	10.00
4b	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	160	75	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₃ O ₄	16.00	18.00	14.00	17.00
4c	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ , OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	185	71	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₃ O ₃	17.80	15.00	16.00	16.00
4d	<i>o</i> -OCOCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	212	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₃ O ₄	13.00	18.00	17.00	15.00
4e	<i>o</i> -OH, C ₆ H ₄	209	68	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₃ O ₃	14.00	17.00	21.00	18.00
4f	<i>p</i> -Cl, OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	168	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₃ S ₃ O ₃ Cl	15.00	17.00	19.00	17.00
4g	<i>o</i> -OH, <i>m</i> -Cl, C ₆ H ₃	223	73	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₃ O ₃ Cl				
4h	3,5-NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄	207	68	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₅ S ₃ O ₆				
4i	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ , <i>p</i> -Cl, C ₆ H ₃	157	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₃ S ₃ O ₂ Cl				
Standard (Streptomycin)					20.00	22.00	20.00	21.00

R = (a) *p*-ClC₆H₄, (b) *p*-NO₂C₆H₄, (c) *p*-CH₃, OCH₂C₆H₄, (d) *o*-OCOCH₃C₆H₄, (e) *o*-OH, C₆H₄, (f) *p*-Cl, OCH₂C₆H₄, (g) *o*-OH, *m*-Cl, C₆H₃, (h) 2,4-NO₂, C₆H₄, (i) *m*-CH₃, *p*-Cl, C₆H₃

Scheme 1

and chloroacetone (0.1 mmol) in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ in dry acetone was refluxed on an oil bath for 20 h, cooled and separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield (83%), m.p. 178 °C; IR (KBr) : 1710 (>C=O), ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.15 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.1 (2H, s, SCH₂), 7.1–7.6 (4H, m, ArH) ppm.

2-(*S*-2'-Arylidenehydrazidopropanoyl)-1,3-benzothiazole (3) :

The mixture of compound 2 (0.25 mmol), substituted aryl hydrazide (0.25 mmol), 2–3 drops of glacial acetic acid in 5 ml of ethanol was refluxed on an oil bath for 4 h, cooled and the separated solid recrystallised from DMF. 3a, yield (80%), m.p. 155 °C, IR (KBr) : 1610 (C=N), 1690 (>C=O), 3310 (NH), ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 2.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.85 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 7–7.9 (8H, m, ArH),

9.7 (1H, brs, NH, exchangeable with D₂O) ppm. 3b, yield (82%), m.p. 143 °C, IR (KBr) : 1610 (C=N), 1685 (>C=O), 3310 (NH), ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 2.31 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.9 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 7.1–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 9.5 (1H, brs, NH, exchangeable with D₂O) ppm. 3c, yield (75%), m.p. 139 °C, IR (KBr) : 1615 (C=N), 1689 (>C=O), 3310 (NH), ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.25 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.7 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 7.1–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 8.7 (1H, brs, NH, exchangeable with D₂O) ppm. 3d, m.p. 200 °C; 3e, m.p. 182 °C; 3f, m.p. 152 °C; 3g, m.p. 200 °C; 3h, m.p. 190 °C; 3i, m.p. 140 °C.

S-(3-Acylamino-2-methyl-4-oxothiazolidin-2-yl)-methyl-1,3-benzothiazole (4) :

The mixture of 3a (0.01 mmol) and mercaptoacetic

acid (0.01 mmol) in 1,4-dioxane containing 2–3 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on oil bath for 10 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in to ice-water mixture, filtered and the recrystallised from ethanol. **4a**, yield (72%), m.p. 205 °C, IR (KBr) : 1685 (>C=O), 1743 (thiazolidinone C=O), 3310 (NH), ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.6 (2H, s, cyclic S-CH₂), 4.5 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 6.9–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 13.2 (1H, brs, NH, exchangeable with D₂O) ppm. **4b**, yield (75%), m.p. 160 °C, IR (KBr) : 1690 (>C=O), 1720 (thiazolidinone C=O), 3310 (NH), ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.8 (2H, s, cyclic S-CH₂), 4.3 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 7–7.8 (8H, m, ArH), 12.5 (1H, brs, NH, exchangeable with D₂O) ppm. **4c**, yield (71%), m.p. 185 °C, IR (KBr) : 1615 (C=N), 1687 (>C=O), 1740 (thiazolidinone C=O), 3310 (NH), ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 2.15 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.32 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.9 (2H, s,

cyclic S-CH₂), 4.4 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 6.8–8.2 (8H, m, ArH), 10.53 (1H, brs, NH, exchangeable with D₂O) ppm.

All the compounds of the series were synthesized by adopting similar methodology. Their physical data of synthesized compounds have been incorporated in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank to the Director, RSIC, Punjab University, Chandigarh for spectral analysis.

References

1. Geoffrey Wells, Philip R. Lowe and Malcolm F. G. Stevens, *Arkivoc*, 2000, **1**, 779; Sushilkumar S. Bahekar and Devanand B. Shinde, *J. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **47**, 237; V. I. Kelarev, K. I. Kobrakov and I. I. Rybina, *Chem. Heterocyclic Compd.*, 2003, **39**; V. Ingale, A. Sawale, R. Ingale and R. Mane, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2001, **40**, 124.